

INTEGRATING A MULTI-DISCIPLINARY APPROACH FOR IMPROVING ANIMAL HEALTH

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ABSTRACT

Globally, the health of livestock and companion animals plays a vital role in improving the livelihood of the human population. For more than a century, animal health has been as important as in improving the socio-economic status of the people. The multidisciplinary efforts taken all over the world on animal health and production provide a way for a sustainable income source. Livestock, pet and wild animal disease control requires lots of effort from different health sectors, governmental policies and societal interests. Disease surveillance, preventive measures, and correct and advanced treatment approaches will greatly improve animal health and welfare.

KEYWORDS: One health, CDC, biosecurity, zoonotic, climate change

INTRODUCTION

Through dialogue and cooperation between doctors, osteopathic practitioners, veterinarians, wildlife specialists, environmental and public health specialists, dentists, nurses, biomedical engineers, physicists, biochemists, plant pathologists, and others, "One Health" encourages the integration of human, animal, and environmental health.

Although the one health concept has not been widely applied yet, its application has always produced positive synergy by, for instance, using a comparative medicine strategy that integrates clinical medicine and surgery, biological research (including laboratory animal science), environmental health, and public health to better understand disease processes. Eliminating artificial barriers like recurring "turfs" or domains will lead to faster and more significant advancements while maintaining domain uniqueness, according to One Health principles (Cullen *et al.*, 2021).

Research, public health, and individual human health are among the tasks of veterinary medicine. In addition to providing important contributions to biomedical research, ecosystem management, public health, food and agricultural systems safety, and biosecurity, the profession is in charge of caring for companion animals, domestic animals that provide food, exotic animals, and wildlife (Fig.1).

Fig.1 Concept of one health, interaction of human, animal and environment (credit: one health commission, USA)

LIVESTOCK HEALTH